

Ceimic as Gaeilge 2024 – Imeacht Seachtain na Gaeilge

Report by: Joseph P. Byrne

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49 Cearnóg Mhuirfeann

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Organisation: ICI Young Chemists Network/Líonra na gCeimiceoirí Óga ICÉ

Event Sponsors

Institute of Chemistry of Ireland, National University of Ireland

Achoimre

Ar 1 Márta, le tús a chur le Seachtain na Gaeilge, bhí imeacht eagraithe ag Líonra na gCeimiceoirí Óga ICÉ (LCÓ) chun deis a thabhairt do chemiceoirí na tíre a gcuid taighde a phlé trí mheáin na Gaeilge. Bhí *Ceimic as Gaeilge 2024* mar an gcéad imeacht dá short riamh.

Bhí *Ceimic as Gaeilge* comh-eagraithe ag Leas-Cathaoirleach LCÓ Cathal Ó Ceallaigh (Ollscoil na Ríonna, Béal Feirste) agus Comhairleoir an Dr Iósaf Ó Beirne (Coláiste na hOllscoile, Baile Átha Cliath), le tacaíocht ó Choiste an LCÓ uile, ach go háirithe Cathaoirleach Seán Byrne. Tá míle buíochas de dhíth ag foireann Ollscoil na hÉireann ag 49 Cearnóg Mhuirfeann Thoir a chuir fáilte fliúirseach agus tacaíocht roimh an imeacht, ach go háirithe Cláraitheoir na hOllscoile an Dr Patrick O'Leary.

Lucht Freastail / Attendees

Bhí thart ar 30 i láthair. **Approximately 30 attended.**

Target audience: academics, postgraduates, ECR (academia), members of the public, policy-makers

Summary

On the 1st of March, to begin Seachtain na Gaeilge, the ICI Young Chemists Network (YCN) organised an event giving opportunities to the country's chemists to discuss their research in the Irish language. *Ceimic as Gaeilge 2024* was the first ever event of its type.

Ceimic as Gaeilge was co-organised by YCN Vice-Chair Cathal Kelly (Queens University Belfast) and Advisor Dr Joseph Byrne (UCD), with support from the rest of the YCN Committee, in particular Chair Seán Byrne. Sincere appreciation also to the team of the National University of Ireland at 49 Merrion Square East who heartily welcomed and supported the event, especially Registrar of the NUI, Dr Patrick O'Leary.

Clár / Programme

Table 1. Clár ama an lae. The timetable of the day.

Time/Am		Cathaoirleach
13:30	Fáilte γ Cuid 1	Cathal Ó Ceallaigh (QUB)
14:45	Sos Caife	
15:00	Cuid 2 γ Comhrá	Iósaf Ó Beirne (UCD)

Íomhá 1. Na cainteoirí uile a ghlac páirt i gCeimic as Gaeilge 2024. All of the speakers who participated in Ceimic as Gaeilge 2024.

Imeachtaí

D'oscail Cathal Ó Ceallaigh imeachtaí an lae le fáilte a chuir roimh na aoí a tháinig trín sneachta gan choinne a thit ar maidin. Faraor theip ar cúpla daoine freastail ar an imeacht i mbliana mar gheall ar iompair poiblí teoranta an lae.

Fáilte 1 Cuid 1

Chuir an Dr **Patrick O'Leary**, Clárathóir OÉ, fáilte foirmiúil roimh na toiscáirí chuig an ionaid. Dúirt sé go raibh lúchair ar OÉ an imeacht a óstáil, ag cur leis "Cuireann ár bplean straitéiseach de cheangal orainn dul chun cinn a dhéanamh lenár gcuid cumas sa Ghaeilge agus le tacú le imeachtaí mar seo." Go dtí cúpla bliain ó shin, bhí an Dr O'Leary ina léachtóir ceimice ag Ollscoil na Gaillimhe, agus ghlac sé an deis a bheith páirteach sa chomhdháil trí chur i láthair taighde ar shintéis na gcatalaíoch nua. Úsáidtear na catalaíochí seo in imoibrithe atá tábhachtach d'ullmhú cógaisíochta. Déanann siad na imoibriú níos éifeachtaí agus níos iontaoifa.

Chuir **Maitiú Ó Ciarnáin (COBÁC)** ó Ghrúpa Paul Evans tús le léirithe na mic léinn iarchéime, á phlé a chuid taithe taighde sa cheimic orgánach. Tá *N*-heitrichiorcail sáithithe mar cheann de na móitíf struchtúrach is comónta i ndrugaí agus i dtáirgí nádúrtha. De thoradh seo tá an-tábhacht ag baint le forbairt imoibrithe nua i dtreo na móilíní seo a

Proceedings

Cathal Kelly opened the day's proceedings by welcoming all the attendees who came through the unexpected snow that fell that morning. Unfortunately, some people were unable to attend due to the day's limited public transport.

Welcome and Part 1

Dr **Patrick O'Leary**, Registrar of NUI, formally welcomed delegates to the venue. He said NUI was delighted to host the event, adding "Our strategic plan commits us to developing our abilities in Irish and to supporting events like this." Until a few years ago, Dr O'Leary was a chemistry lecturer in University of Galway, and he took the opportunity to participate in the conference, presenting research on the synthesis of new catalysts. These catalysts are used in reactions that are important for pharmaceutical preparation. They make the reactions more efficient and reliable.

Matthew Kiernan (UCD) from the Paul Evans Group put a start to the postgraduate student talks, discussing his experience with organic chemistry research. Saturated *N*-heterocycles are some of the most common structural motifs in drugs and natural products. As a result of this, great importance is associated with developing new reactions towards creating these molecules in effective

cruthú i mbealach éifeachtúil agus roghnaitheach. Rinne Maitiú cur síos ar iarrachtaí s'aige agus a chomhoibrí chun teacht ar dhá imoibriú nua; (1) Sintéis neamh-shiméadrach pioróilidíní trí chatalú tiacarbamáite; agus (2) Sintéis raicéamach aiseitidíní trí úsáid heacseafluairiseaprópánól.

Labhair **Niamh Ní Shé** ó Ghrúpa Gunnlaugsson (*CnaT*) faoin a cuid oibre le “Móilíní atá idirghaolmhar go meicniúil agus Micreascópacht”, ach go háirithe caitéineáin agus rothacsáin. Labhair sí faoin gceimic formhóilíneach, steiríceimic mheicniúil agus stair na ceimice seo agus na móilíní atá faoi thaighde aici. Thaispeán Niamh aidhmeanna a cuid tionscadail, ina measc úsáid compléisc lantanóidigh mar stopadóirí rothacsáine, agus cruthú braitheoirí nó ghéataí loighic le rothacsáin bunaithe ar **btp** (2,6-bis(1,2,3-tríasól-4-il)piridín).

Úsáideann a grúpa taighde an moitíf **btp** mar theimpléad ar na struchtúir móilíneacha seo. Phléigh sí an sintéis, an imoibriú ‘clíc’ coparchatalaithe agus na turgnamh a bharrfheabhsaigh na dáil imoibrithe chun macraichíogal **btp** a dhéanamh go roghnaitheach. Thaispeán Niamh íomhánna leictreomhicreascóip scanacháin a léirígh na struchtúir éagsúla cruthaithe le úsáid tuaslagóirí difriúil. Chuir an chuid seo den chaint béim ar féidireacht na móilíní seo féinchóimeáil a dhéanamh. Mar achoimre, bhí an caint seo faoin na haidhmeanna agus scóip a bhaineann lena cuid oibre, an sintéis a úsáidtear agus na n-uirlis anailíse a úsáidtear sa thionscadal.

Cuireadh tús leis an gcur i láthair ag **Eoghan Ó Curnáin** leis an taighde ar lotnaidicídí foirmilíthe le micreacapsúl in-bhithmhillte, a rinneadh ar shocrúchán le *Life Scientific*. Ina dhiaidh sin, pléadh sintéis na substráite agus barrfheabhsú an imoibrithe DAAA Pd-chatalaithe de chomhdhúil heitrea-fáinneach ina bhfuil sulfair acu, atá ar siúil aige i nGrúpa Uí Gadhra (*COBÁC*). Ar deireadh, soláthraíodh cúlra agus plean an tionscadail chun imoibriú Suzuki neamh-shiméadrach a bhaint amach, agus é seo a chur i bhfeidhmin in ullmhú liogann-*P,N* ciriúla i leith na haise.

and selective ways. Matthew described the efforts he and his team have made to come up with two new reactions; (1) Asymmetric synthesis of pyrrolidines through thio-carbamate catalysis; and (2) Racemic synthesis of azetidines through the use of hexafluoroisopropanol.

Niamh O’Shea from the Gunnlaugsson Group (*TCD*) was talking about her work with “Mechanically Interlocking Molecules and Microscopy”, especially catenanes and rotaxanes. She spoke about supramolecular chemistry, mechanostereochemistry and the history behind this chemistry and the molecules she is researching. Niamh showed the aims of her Project being the use of lanthanides as stoppers for **btp** (2,6-bis(1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)pyridine) rotaxanes and the aims for the creation of sensors or logic gates with the rotaxanes.

Her research group uses the **btp** motif for the templating of these molecular structures. She discussed the synthesis, Cu-azide click reactions and experiments to optimise reaction conditions to selectively produce **btp** macrocycles. Niamh displayed Scanning Electron Microscopy Images and the different structures created when you use different solvents. This part of the talk highlighted these molecules’ ability to self-assemble. In summary, the talk was about the aims and scope of the work, the synthesis being deployed, and the analytical instruments being used in the project.

Eoghan Courtney’s presentation began with an overview of the research into developing a biodegradable microcapsule pesticide product, which he did on placement in *Life Scientific*. Following that, the synthesis of the substrate and the initial optimization of the Pd-catalyzed DAAA reaction of sulfur-containing heterocycles that is ongoing in the Guiry Group (*UCD*) were discussed. Lastly, the background and project outline for achieving asymmetric Suzuki reaction in the preparation of axially chiral *P,N*-ligands were provided.

Labhair An Dr **Iósaf Ó Beirne** (COBÁC) faoin taighde atá ar siúl sa ghrúpa 's aige le coimpléisc miotail maisithe le carbaihiodráite. I gcomhthéacs an dúshlán frithsheasmhachta in aghaidh ábhar frithmhiocróbach, tá siad ag iarraidh dhíriú ar pataiginí i mbealach nua, ina bhaintear feidhm as próitéiní áirthe a nascann le carbaihiodráite (ar a ghlaotar 'leictiní'). Rinne Joe cur síos ar dhá sort glicea-bhraisle miotal-lárnach, bunaithe ar scafall **btp** (2,6-bis(1,2,3-tríasól-4-il)piridín) nó **dpa** (2,6-décarbocsaipiridín). Bhí éifeacht frith-bhithscao ag coimpléisc **btp** Ru(II) nach raibh le fáil leis an liogann amháin - in aineoinn go raibh siad neamh-bhaictéiricídeach. Rinneadh réimse coimpléisc **dpa** le miotail éagsúla, ach bhí an éifeacht is mó frith-*Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ag coimpléisc eorapiam(III). Léirigh sé fresin an féidireacht a bhí ag coimpléisc galachtósíde Tb(III) (le spáisire oiriúnach) mar braiteora leictiní lonnrachta, a éirigh níos gile nuair a bhí leictin a nascann galachtós ann.

Gabh an Dr Ó Beirne buíochas leis an lucht a tháinig inniu agus tharraing sé aird ar saibhreas an phlé a bhí ar siúl trí cheisteanna agus freagra suimiúla i ndiadh gach léiriú. Soláthraigh sé fiúntas an lae. Leis an méid sin ráite, ghlacadh sos caife agus cainte neamh-fhormúil.

Dr **Joseph Byrne** (UCD) spoke about the research that is underway in his group with carbohydrate-functionalised metal complexes. In the context of the challenge of antimicrobial resistance (AMR), they are trying to target pathogens in a new way, making use of specific carbohydrate-binding proteins (called 'lectins'). Joe described two kinds of metal-centred glyco-cluster, based on the scaffolds **btp** (2,6-bis(1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)pyridine) or **dpa** (dipicolinic acid). Ru(II) **btp** complexes had an anti-biofilm effect that was not observed with the ligand alone - despite not being bactericidal. A range of **dpa** complexes with various metals were made, but the europium(III) complexes had the largest anti-*Pseudomonas aeruginosa* effect. He also demonstrated the capability of galactoside Tb(III) complexes (with appropriate spacer) as luminescent lectin sensors, that became brighter when a galactose-binding lectin was present.

Dr Byrne thanked the attendees for coming today and drew attention to the wealth of discussion that was taking place through interesting questions and answers after each talk. This demonstrated the value of the day. With that said, a break for coffee and informal discussion took place.

Íomhá 2. (ar chlé) Sneachta an lae ar doras Oilscoill na hÉireann; (ar dheis) An Dr Patrick O'Leary, Cláráitheoir OÉ leis an Dr Iósaf Ó Beirne agus Cathal Ó Ceallaigh a d'eagraigh an imeacht. (left) The day's snowfall on the door of the National University of Ireland; (right) Dr Patrick O'Leary, Registrar of the NUI with Dr Joseph Byrne and Cathal Kelly who organised the event.

Cuid 2

Thosaigh an dara seisiún leis an cainteoir a tháinig ón áit is faide don imeacht inniu. Rinne **Cathal Ó Ceallaigh** (*CnaRBF*) cur síos ar a thaighde i leachtanna scagacha. Léiríú go gcrúthaíonn scagacht méadú ar ionsú gáis na leachtanna seo. Aimsíú nach seo an cás nuair a n-úsáidtear CO₂. Cuireadh an locht ar "spás curtha amú", coincheap nua i leachtanna scagacha. Cruthaíonn mórchoír steireach an óstmhóilín spás nach úsáideann na mhóilíní gáis, agus cruthaíonn seo laghdu ar an ionsú gáis. Rinneadh cur síos ar bealaí a d'fhéadfadh an spás curtha amú seo a laghdú: trí méid na móilíní tuaslagóirí a laghdú agus scagacht éifeachtacht an óstmhóilín a mhéadú.

An teideal a bhí ag léiríú **Eoin Mac Aoidh Pasquetti** (*COBÁC*), ó Ghrúpa Grace Morgan, ná "Saol Maighnéadach an Adaimh: Réamhrá ar Aistriú Guairne". Deineadh plé ar aistriú guairne; Cén rud é?, Conas a scrúdaítear?, is cad iad na feidhmeanna a bhaineann leis? Deineadh cur síos bunúsach ar Cheimic Chomordánaithe is ar an slí a éiríonn aistriú amach as an mbaint atá ann idir stát guairne an adaimh agus an neart atá sa réimse liogainn. Deineadh plé ar na teicnící is tábhachtaí a bhaineann le aistriú guairne agus ar an eolas is féidir a bhaint astu.

Ar deireadh, tugadh samplaí dosna hábhair gurbh fhéidir aistriú guairne a chur i bhfeidhm iontu agus ábhair go bhfuil sé i bhfeidhm iontu cheana féin.

Labhair **Aoibheann Ní Chonchubhair** (*COBÁC*) ó Ghrúpa Uí Ghadhra ar fiosrúchán ar an imoibriú Diels-Alder neamhshiméadreach. Is grúpa sintéis neamhshiméadreach é an Grúpa Uí Ghadhra, agus sa chur i láthair seo bhíodar ag díriú ar an úsáid do chuiditheoir ciriúlacht mar stratéis chun neamhshiméadreach a chruthú. Ag úsáid an imoibriú dé-éin a bhí dearrtha acu cheana féin i gcomhair móilíní nítrigin, agus le spreagadh ón obair Evans i 1984, d'úsáidtear an imoibriú sin chun dé-éin a chur ar an chuiditheoir ciriúlacht, in ionad ar an dé-éinifileach.

Part 2

The second session began with the speaker who had traveled the furthest for today's event. **Cathal Kelly** (*QUB*) described his research into porous liquids. Porous liquids normally show enhanced gas uptakes. It was highlighted how this wasn't the case when CO₂ was employed as the gas being absorbed. This was blamed on "wasted space", a new concept in porous liquids. The steric bulk of the host molecules creates a space which gas molecules don't occupy which leads to a reduction in the overall gas uptake. Different ways of reducing this wasted space were described: reducing the size of the solvent molecules and increasing the effective porosity of the host molecules.

The title of the talk presented by **Eoin McGee Pasquetti** (*UCD*) from the Group of Grace Morgan was "The Magnetic Life of the atom: Introduction to Spin Crossover". The topic of spin exchange was discussed; What is it? How can it be examined? And what are its applications? A basic description of Coordination Chemistry was given, and of the manner that crossover gets out of the link between the spin state of the atom and the strength that is in a range of ligands. Important techniques related to spin crossover, and on the information that may be gleaned from them, was also discussed.

Finally, examples of subjects in which spin crossover could be utilised as well as areas where they are already in use.

Aoibheann O'Connor (*UCD*) from the Guiry Group spoke about the investigation on the asymmetric Diels-Alder reaction. The Guiry group is an asymmetric synthesis group, and this presentation was directed on their use of chiral auxiliaries as a strategy for inducing asymmetry. Using a previously designed dienylation reaction for nitrogen containing molecules, and drawing on inspiration from the work of Evans in 1984, they used this same dienylation reaction to install a diene on the chiral auxiliary, instead of installing a dienophile on it. They have prepared 12 examples of the diene with the

Chruthaítear thart ar 12 shampla don dé-éin le cuiditheoir ciriúlacht le toradh suas go dtí 97%, níos mó ná 50 shampla don táirge Diels-Alder le toradh suas go dtí 70% agus id suas go dtí 93:7, agus 5 shampla don táirge gan an cuiditheoir ciriúlacht le toradh suas go dtí 81% agus ie suas go dtí 92%. D'éirigh leo structúr criostail a bhaint amach don dé-éin, dos na tháirge DA agus don táirge gan an cuiditheoir ciriúlacht. Bhíodar in ann eolas cruinn faoin structúr agus neamhshiméadrach tríd an córas anailíse seo, nach fhéadfaí stadéir le anailís AMN in aonar.

chiral auxiliary with yields up to 97%, more than 50 examples of the Diels-Alder product in yields up to 70% and dr up to 93:7, and 5 examples of the product without the chiral auxiliary in yields up to 81% and ee up to 92%. They accessed XRD structures of the dienes, the Diels-Alder products and the compounds without the chiral auxiliary. They could obtain crucial structural information from this method of analysis that would not be possible with the use of NMR analysis alone.

Rinne **An Dr. Gearóid Ó Maille (CET)**, a bhí ag glacadh páirt ón mBruiséil ar MS Teams, cur síos ar a chosán gairme féin, ón saotharlann go ról mar Oifigeach Eolaíochta sa gCoimisiún Eorpach. Thug sé eolas ar dheiseanna maoinithe do thaighdeoirí faoin gClár Réime "Fís Eorpach", le béim ar chlár na Comhairle Eorpaí um Thaighde (CET). Is e an CET príomhghaoinitheoir an Chomisiún Eorpaí do thaighde ar thús cadhnaíochta, agus tá raon deontais curtha ar fáil do eolaithe ag céimeanna gairme difriúla.

Tugadh chun cuimhne freisin an nasc láidir a bhí idir ceimic agus an Ghaeilge in Ollscoil na Gaillimhe: mar shampla, scríobh an réabhlóidí agus an t-ollamh clúiteach Thomas Dillon (ceann scoile ó 1919), an chéad leabhar ceimice i nGaeilge. Lean an meas seo ar ár dteanga sna glúnta a lean é: rinne na ceannairí scoile, an tOll. Proinsias Ó Colla, an tOll. Seán Ó Cinnéide agus an tOll. Ristéard N. de Buitléir, gan dearmad a dhéanamh ar na Oll Breandán Ó Cochláin, a gcion féin go dúthrachtach leis an nGaeilge a choinneáil beo sa gceimic. Labhair Gearóid ar an ádh a bhí air go raibh cuid mhór dá chuid léachtanna ceimice trí mheán na Gaeilge agus é ina mhac léinn i nGaillimh, áit ar ghríosaigh an tOll. de Buitléir na mic léinn an fód a sheasamh don teanga trí léiriú don domhan mór gur teanga nua-aimseartha í an Ghaeilge ar féidir í a úsáid le hábhair theicniúla a phlé.

Thug sé ómós don bhaicle leachtóirí a mhúin ceimic trí Ghaeilge i nGaillimh: go háirithe an tOll. Pat McArdle,

Dr Gearóid Ó Máille (ERC), joining from Brussels via MS Teams, described his career path from the laboratory to his current role as a Scientific Officer at the European Commission. He detailed some funding opportunities available for researchers under the "Horizon Europe" Framework Programme, with particular emphasis on the European Research Council (ERC) programme. The ERC is the European Commission's flagship funder for frontier research, and a range of grants are available for scientists at different career stages.

The strong link between chemistry and Irish in the University of Galway was also commemorated: for example, the revolutionary and famous professor Thomas Dillon (head of school from 1919), wrote the first chemistry book in Irish. This respect for the language continued in the subsequent generations: the school leaders Prof Proinsias O'Colla, Prof Seán Ó Cinnéide and Prof Richard (Dick) Butler, not to forget Prof Brendan Coughlan, who each did their share fervently to keep Irish alive in chemistry. Gearóid spoke about how lucky he was to have a large share of his chemistry lectures through the medium of Irish when he was a student in Galway, a place where Prof Butler urged students to stand their ground for the language by demonstrating to the world that Irish was a modern language that could be used to discuss technical matters.

He paid respect to the group of lecturers who taught chemistry through Irish in Galway: especially Prof Pat

criostalagrafaí agus léachtóir den chéad scoth a fuair bás le rí-ghairid in Eanáir na bliana seo, agus an tOll. Mike Hynes, saineolaí ar chineiticí agus treoraí tuisceanach, a cailleadh i 2022. Bhásaigh an tOll de Buitléir go tobann i 2016.

Conclúid

Léirsigh an imeacht seo go raibh sé in-déanta plé leathan ar cúrsaí thaighde ceimice a chur i láthair trí mheáin na Gaeilge, agus go bhfuil éileamh ann freisin san ETIM. Tá súil ag an lucht eagraithe go mbeidh imeacht dá short arís sa thodhchaí.

Buíochas

Táimid fíor-bhuíoch as an tacaíocht a thug Institúid Ceimice an hÉireann, Líonra na gCeimiceoirí Óga, agus Cathoirleach an Líonra Seán Byrne. Buíochas freisin le foireann Ollscoil na hÉireann as an ionad a chur ar fáil: Cláraitheoir na hOllscoile an Dr Patrick O'Leary agus Cora Lenihan, ach go háirithe. Bhí tacaíocht bríomhar ó na urlábhraí uile a ghlac páirt riachtanach don imeacht uailmhianach seo – míle bhuíochas dóibh a thug a gcuid ama don tionscadal.

McArdle, a first-rate crystallographer and lecturer, who died very recently in January of this year, and Prof Mike Hynes, an expert in kinetics and understanding teacher, who passed away in 2022. Prof Butler died suddenly in 2016.

Conclusions

This event demonstrated that it is completely possible to present broad discussion on topics of chemistry research in the Irish language, and that there is also demand for this in STEM. The organisers how that events of this type will take place again in the future.

Acknowledgements

We are very grateful for the support of the Institute of Chemistry of Ireland, the Young Chemists Network and Network Chair Seán Byrne. Thanks also to the team of the National University of Ireland for making a venue available: Registrar Dr Patrick O'Leary and Cora Lenihan in particular. The enthusiastic support of the all the speakers who took part was vital to this ambitious event – sincere thanks to those who committed their time to this project.

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